

IKKINCHI TARTIBLI SIRTLARNI GALILEY ALMASHTIRISHI YORDAMIDA KLASSIFIKATSIYA QILISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada uch o'lchovli galiley fazosidagi sirtning umumiy tenglamasidan foydalanib uning klassifikatsiyasi ko'rsatilgan va bu fazoda sirtlar uchun muxim bo'lgan ba'zi teoremlar isbotlangan. Galiley xarakatidagi sirt deformatsiyasini tadbiri ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: galiley fazosi, ikkinchi tartibli sirt, galiley harakati, klassifikatsiya, ellips, parabola, giperbola.

Abstract. This paper provides a classification of surfaces in three-dimensional Galilean space based on their general equations. Several fundamental theorems concerning surfaces within this space are formulated and proven. Furthermore, the application of surface deformation under Galilean transformations is demonstrated.

Keywords: Galilean space, second-order surface, Galilean motion, classification, ellipse, parabola, hyperbola.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена классификация поверхностей в трехмерном галилеевом пространстве на основе их общего уравнения. Доказаны некоторые важные теоремы для поверхностей в этом пространстве. Рассмотрено приложение деформации поверхностей при галилеевых движениях.

Ключевые слова: галилеево пространство, поверхность второго порядка, галилеево движение, классификация, эллипс, парабола, гипербола.

Uch o'lchovli galiley fazosida ikkinchi tartibli sirt tenglamasini soddalashtirish uni klasifikatsiya qilish va qaysi sirt tipiga mansub ekanligini aniqlash.

Bizga $\vec{X} = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ va $\vec{Y} = (y_1, y_2, y_3)$ vektorlar uch o'lchovli affin fazosida berilgan bo'lsin. Agar skalyar ko'paytma:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 y_1, \text{ agar } \Rightarrow x_1 \neq 0, y_1 \neq 0 \\ x_2 y_2 + x_3 y_3, \text{ agar } \Rightarrow x_1 = 0, y_1 = 0 \end{cases}$$

Shaklda aniqlansa bu affin fazo uch o'lchovli galiley fazosi deyiladi.

Ixtiyoriy $\vec{X} = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ vektorning normasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} |x_1|, \text{ agar } \Rightarrow x_1 \neq 0 \\ \sqrt{x_2^2 + x_3^2}, \text{ agar } \Rightarrow x_1 = 0 \end{cases}$$

Agar ikkita $M(a_1, a_2, a_3), N(b_1, b_2, b_3)$ nuqtalar berilgan bo'lsa ular orasidagi masofa:

$$\begin{cases} |b_1 - a_1|, \text{ agar } \Rightarrow a_1 \neq b_1 \\ \sqrt{(b_2 - a_2)^2 + (b_3 - a_3)^2}, \text{ agar } \Rightarrow a_1 = b_1 \end{cases}$$

Formula orqali topiladi.

Yevklid fazosida bo'lgani kabi galiley fazosida ham ikki xil harakat parallel ko'cherish va burchakga burishdan iborat. Uch o'lchovli galiley fazosida harakat tenglamalari quyidagicha bo'ladi.

$$\begin{cases} x' = x + a \\ y' = h_1x + y \cos \alpha - z \sin \alpha + b \\ z' = h_2x + y \sin \alpha + z \cos \alpha + c \end{cases}$$

Asosiy qism:

Sirtlarni o'rganishda uni biror nuqtasi atrofida tekshirish muhim. Sirtni nuqtasi atrofida uning umumiy tenglamasi orqali tekshirish mumkin.

Bizga:

$$a_{11}x^2 + a_{22}y^2 + a_{33}z^2 + 2a_{12}xy + 2a_{13}xz + 2a_{23}yz + 2a_{14}x + 2a_{24}y + 2a_{34}z + a_{44} = 0$$

Ikkinchi tartibli sirt umumiy tenglamasi bilan berilgan bo'lsin.

Bu yerda $a_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}$ va noldan farqli.

Qulay bo'lishi uchun sirt umumiy tenglamasini qayta yozib olamiz:

$$a_{11}x''^2 + a_{22}y''^2 + a_{33}z''^2 + 2a_{12}x''y'' + 2a_{13}x''z'' + 2a_{23}y''z'' + 2a_{14}x'' + 2a_{24}y'' + 2a_{34}z'' + a_{44} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Birinchi almashtirish markazni ko'chirish:

$$\begin{cases} x'' = x' + a \\ y'' = y' + b \\ z'' = z' + c \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

(2) ni (1) ga olib borib qo'yamiz, bundan maqsad birinchi darajali hadlarni 0 ga aylantirish.

Natijada:

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}a + a_{12}b + a_{13}c + a_{14} = 0 \\ a_{12}a + a_{22}b + a_{23}c + a_{24} = 0 \\ a_{13}a + a_{23}b + a_{33}c + a_{34} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Ushbu sistema hosil bo'ladi. (3) ni qanoatlantiradigan (a,b,c) nuqta bor deb olsak, yani:

$$K_3 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} \neq 0$$

($K_3=0$ bo'lgan holini keyingi ishlarda ko'rib chiqamiz!)

Bo'lgan hol uchun (1) quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$a_{11}x'^2 + a_{22}y'^2 + a_{33}z'^2 + 2a_{12}x'y' + 2a_{13}x'z' + 2a_{23}y'z' + a'_{44} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Bu yerda:

$$a'_{44} = a_{44} + a_{14}a + a_{24}b + a_{34}c$$

(3) sistemadan a , b va c larni topib o'rniga qo'ysak:

$$a'_{44} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} & a_{34} \\ a_{14} & a_{24} & a_{34} & a_{44} \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}} = \frac{K_4}{K_3}$$

Bu yerda

$$K_4 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} & a_{34} \\ a_{14} & a_{24} & a_{34} & a_{44} \end{vmatrix} \quad K_3 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}.$$

Ikkinchi almashtirish: burchakga burish.

$$\begin{cases} x' = x \\ y' = h_1 x + y \cos \alpha - z \sin \alpha \\ z' = h_2 x + y \sin \alpha + z \cos \alpha \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

(5) almashtirishni (4) ga qo'yamiz va soddalashtiramiz. Bundan maqsad xy , xz va yz oldidagi hadlarni 0 ga aylantirishdir.

$$\begin{cases} (a_{33} - a_{22}) \sin 2a + 2a_{23} \cos 2a = 0 \\ (a_{22} \cos a + a_{23} \sin a)h_1 + (a_{33} \sin a + a_{23} \cos a)h_2 = -a_{12} \cos a - a_{13} \sin a \\ (-a_{22} \sin a + a_{23} \cos a)h_1 + (a_{33} \cos a - a_{23} \sin a)h_2 = a_{12} \sin a - a_{13} \cos a \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

(6) sistemani yechib h_1, h_2, α larni topib olamiz.

$$\begin{cases} \tan 2a = \frac{2a_{23}}{a_{22} - a_{33}} \\ \tan a = \frac{-(a_{22} - a_{33}) \pm \sqrt{(a_{22} - a_{33})^2 + 4a_{23}^2}}{2a_{23}}, a_{23} \neq 0 \\ h_1 = \frac{a_{13}a_{23} - a_{23}a_{12}}{a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}^2} \\ h_2 = \frac{a_{12}a_{23} - a_{22}a_{13}}{a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}^2}, a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}^2 \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

Bu yerda $a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}^2 \neq 0$ deb olganmiz teng nol bo'lgan hollarini keyingi ishlarimizda ko'rib chiqamiz!

Natijada (4) tenglama quyidagicha ko'rinishga keladi:

$$Ax^2 + By^2 + Cz^2 = D$$

Bu yerda:

$$A = \frac{a_{11}a_{22}a_{33} - a_{11}a_{23}^2 - a_{33}a_{12}^2 - a_{22}a_{13}^2 + 2a_{12}a_{13}a_{23}}{a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}^2}$$

$$B = \frac{a_{22} + a_{33} + \sqrt{(a_{22} - a_{33})^2 + 4a_{23}^2}}{2}$$

$$C = \frac{a_{22} + a_{33} - \sqrt{(a_{22} - a_{33})^2 + 4a_{23}^2}}{2}$$

$$D = -a'_{44}$$

Endi koefitsientlarning mos qiymatlarida klassifikatsiya qilamiz:

1) Agar $A > 0$, $B > 0$, $C > 0$, $D > 0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} + \frac{z^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/C}\right)^2} = 1$$

Ellipsoid ko'rinishiga keladi.

2) Agar $A > 0$, $B > 0$, $C > 0$, $D < 0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} + \frac{z^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/C}\right)^2} = -1$$

Mavhum Ellipsoid ko'rinishiga keladi.

3) Agar $A > 0$, $B > 0$, $C < 0$, $D > 0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} - \frac{z^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/C}\right)^2} = 1$$

Bir pallali giperboloid ko'rinishiga keladi.

4) Agar $A > 0$, $B > 0$, $C < 0$, $D < 0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} - \frac{z^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/C}\right)^2} = -1$$

Ikki pallali giperboloid ko'rinishiga keladi.

5) Agar $A > 0$, $B > 0$, $C > 0$, $D > 0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} + \frac{z^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/C}\right)^2} = 1$$

Ellipsoid ko'rinishiga keladi.

6) Agar $A > 0$, $B > 0$, $C = 0$, $D > 0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} = 1$$

Elliptik silindr ko'rinishiga keladi.

7) Agar $A > 0$, $B < 0$, $C = 0$, $D > 0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} - \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} = 1$$

Giperbolik silindr ko'rinishiga keladi.

8) Agar $A>0$, $B>0$, $C=0$, $D<0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} = -1$$

Mavhum Elliptik silindr ko'rinishiga keladi.

9) Agar $A>0$, $B<0$, $C=0$, $D=0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} - \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} = 0$$

Kesishuvchi tekislik ko'rinishiga keladi.

10) Agar $A>0$, $B>0$, $C=0$, $D=0$ bo'lsa:

$$\frac{x^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/A}\right)^2} + \frac{y^2}{\left(\sqrt{D/B}\right)^2} = 0$$

Mavhum kesishuvchi tekislik ko'rinishiga keladi.

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